

Full report on Virtual Mobility Grant (VMG):
MWR observation minus background brightness
temperature monitoring
COST action number: CA18235

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Abstract (VMG Objectives)

Monitoring observed microwave radiometer (MWR) brightness temperatures (T_B) against a model background (O-B), during scenes with no liquid water clouds present, can be a valuable quality assurance tool for detecting systematic errors. The O-B method can provide insights into long-term drifts of instrument uncertainties in a statistical analysis, as well as help with online near-real-time quality monitoring. Therefore, the main objective of this VMG is to establish a framework of continuous O-B monitoring that can be applied to network configurations of MWR. In a first step a centralized MWR processing tool is established to implement O-B quality control criteria for a network of instruments. Also, besides extracting long-term data sets of numerical weather prediction (NWP) model profiles, a suitable observation operator to convert atmospheric profiles into simulated T_B (serving as the background) is implemented into a software tool. Different applications of O-B methods are shown that will be used to improve the implementation of the operational monitoring.

This collaborative VMG initiative is being implemented within the Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS, Häme et al. (2018)). In ACTRIS, the Centre for Cloud Remote Sensing (CCRES) operates and maintains a network of MWR, and is responsible for quality assurance and support of participating facilities. For an improved T_B quality control of MWR single channels, the O-B monitoring will be a valuable tool for long-term systematic drift detection and calibration recommendations for station operators. An existing framework of utilising NWP model profiles in the cloud remote sensing data centre unit (CLU) will be further extended to support efforts towards operational O-B monitoring. With a suitable observation operator, background T_B can be derived and compared to MWR measurements (also stored at CLU). The criteria that will be provided in the central processing tool, to check the data quality, can also be implemented at stations or networks outside ACTRIS (like EUMETNET's profiling network E-PROFILE, Rüfenacht et al. (2021)), if such O-B monitoring for MWR is being performed.

In terms of the COST Action CA18235 objective and deliverables the VMG contributes to D3.3 (Recommendations and prototype tools for centralised processing and network monitoring) through the established methods and processing tools, which result in harmonized data generation and common metadata formats of network data streams. Furthermore, the resulting MWR quality control mechanisms, which can be used for operational data quality assessment, are a substantial part of D4.1 (Recommendations for configuration, operation, calibration, quality control).

1 Introduction

In general, ground-based passive microwave radiometers (MWRs) are used to derive information on the vertical structure of the atmosphere, especially in the lower troposphere, which also includes liquid water clouds. Measured radiances by MWRs are expressed as brightness temperatures (T_B), and originate from two frequency ranges (K- and V-band) along absorption lines of water vapor and oxygen, as well as from window regions suitable for liquid water cloud observations. Profile information on temperature and humidity can be retrieved together with integrated quantities of water vapor and the cloud liquid water path (LWP). Performing specific elevation scans allows to improve the vertical resolution for temperature profiles in the atmospheric boundary-layer. The MWR instruments are capable to be operated continuously and unattended, and provide temporal highly resolved observations of up to 1s. This makes them valuable for improving NWP and climate models by studying the atmospheric water cycle, including cloud dynamics (Westwater, Crewell, and Mätzler 2004).

MWR data are also applied in the synergistic algorithm Cloudnet (Illingworth et al. 2007), which classifies hydrometeors in the cloudy atmosphere by combining several ground-based remote sensing instruments and NWP data. ACTRIS-CCRES aims to provide continuous and harmonized long-term data of cloud properties and the thermodynamic state of the atmosphere. Therefore, Cloudnet represents one of the key components and MWRs are mandatory to qualify as an ACTRIS-CCRES compatible station. The so-called Central Facility, responsible for MWRs in the network, is hosted within ACTRIS Germany (ACTRIS-D).

ACTRIS-CCRES will encompass about 30 stations in Europe, including mobile platforms, and covering different climatological zones. This network configuration enables investigations of differences of atmospheric processes and long-term trends between those sites. Some of the participating facilities have been operational already over a decade and Cloudnet products are derived based on site specific setups and processing algorithms. To ensure that the generated data sets can be compared, station operators are required to follow the ACTRIS-CCRES standard operating procedures (SOPs, e.g. [MWR-SOP](#)) and send their raw data files to CLU, which is providing data storage and provision, but also performs centralized processing, including visualization, in order to harmonize the data streams.

Operating instruments in such a network requires a comprehensive assessment of uncertainties to ensure a high quality level of the whole data stream and across all sites. In this sense, near-real-time quality monitoring of data streams can be utilized to help station operators to maintain instruments with notifications when instrument malfunctions are detected. Assessing the quality of long-term data sets, on the other hand, is a crucial part for ensuring continuous operation and unveil degradation and resulting drifts.

In the following, network suitable methods and tools to monitor and assess the quality and long-term stability of MWR instrument uncertainties are described.

Chapter 2 contains a description of the central MWR processing software `MWRpy`, which has been implemented in the Cloudnet framework, and how T_B are simulated to be used in an O-B study. In Chapter 3 O-B results from a long-term drift analysis and field experiment with multiple locations are presented. Chapter 4 gives conclusions and describes how those studies can be used to inform the implementation of an operational O-B monitoring.

2 Methods

In order to provide harmonized O-B monitoring in a MWR network, central processing and quality control software needs to be established together with a method to derive background T_B . In the following, these tools, which are part of ACTRIS, are described in more detail.

2.1 MWR processing software - `MWRpy`

`MWRpy`, as described in Marke et al. (2024), addresses the needs of a centralized processing, quality control of raw data, and deriving standardized output of geophysical MWR products. The Python code is based on the IDL processing software `mwr_pro` (Löhnert 2023) and handles raw data streams from Humidity and Temperature PROfiler (HATPRO) instruments manufactured by Radiometer Physics GmbH (RPG), which represents so far the only instrument type in the ACTRIS-CCRES network. The output format of `MWRpy`, including metadata information, variable names, and file naming of is designed to be compliant with the data structure and naming convention developed together with E-PROFILE. `MWRpy` is therefore improving data compatibility and fosters cross network collaborations. The processing chain, depicted in Figure 1, is replacing the current mode of operation in Cloudnet, which previously relied on pre-processed and non-harmonized MWR data. In this way, `MWRpy` contributes to more data consistency within ACTRIS. Statistical analysis of these long-term data sets, including O-B analysis, is expected to be beneficial not only for atmospheric studies, but also for improving knowledge on instrument operation and maintenance. This will be achieved by monitoring instrument uncertainties and results from mandatory regular absolute calibrations, which should be performed approximately every 6 months (see `MWR-SOP`).

`MWRpy` can be used as a stand-alone software since it covers the full data processing and visualization chain from raw files to higher level products (Fig. 1), but it is also embedded in the Python implementation of the ACTRIS Cloudnet processing scheme `CloudnetPy` (Tukiainen, O'Connor, and Korpinen 2020). At first, the code is designed to perform data quality control, including the mandatory data fields of measured T_B , and instrument specific housekeeping data (HKD) to generate quality flags. For a more efficient instrument failure detection and alerting, and to ensure optimal performances of sensors, a centralized online HKD monitoring tool is being implemented in ACTRIS-CCRES. The tool

Figure 1: Flowchart of the [MWRpy](#) processing chain, with the last two steps being exclusive for the CloudnetPy implementation.

provides a visualization platform and E-mail alerts can be configured to support station operators.

Implementing the O-B framework (for continuous monitoring of T_B drifts) in this first processing step can inform about the necessity of an absolute calibration, and will be included as a statistical quality assessment. Next, auxiliary data, e.g. from weather station, or an infrared radiometer, are combined in a daily netCDF file. Subsequently advanced geophysical parameters are derived by applying retrieval coefficients and stored as two separate daily files, one combining variables originating from elevation scans (e.g. temperature profiles) and the other containing all remaining operating modes (including vertical stare for e.g. LWP). The output of [MWRpy](#) is then harmonized within the Cloudnet processing framework and utilized by CloudnetPy. Together with data streams from other ACTRIS-CCRES instruments, like cloud radar and lidar, synergy products are derived. All resulting files, including instrument calibration, retrieval information, model data, and corresponding visualizations are stored at CLU and accessible through API.

2.2 Radiative transfer

In order to derive background T_B a microwave radiative transfer (RT) model, which computes the propagation of radiation through the atmosphere, is needed. The non-scattering RT is based on simulating absorption and emission of electromagnetic radiation by constituents present in the atmosphere. Here, the Rosenkranz model (Rosenkranz 2017), which accounts for the speed dependence of 22- and 118-GHz line shapes (see Rosenkranz and Cimini (2019)) in an updated version from 2022, was used and considers absorption parameters for oxygen,

water vapor, and nitrogen for clear-air atmospheres in the microwave spectral region. Only clear-sky periods are analyzed to avoid high uncertainties coming from the model and absorption of cloud liquid water. As input, RT models require thermodynamic profiles of the atmosphere (namely pressure, temperature, and humidity) to compute radiances (expressed as T_B) corresponding to the atmospheric state. Together with HATPRO instrument characteristics, this RT model configuration serves as observation operator and is implemented in a Python software package¹, including functions to read input data from several sources, like NWP models, reanalysis, and radiosondes. It is important to note that O-B differences can not only be attributed to instrument uncertainties, but also contain errors from the RT model and systematic NWP model errors. Discriminating between those complex error sources is often not straight forward, since the truth is not known, and should be kept in mind for any comparison.

3 Results

The previously described methods for MWR data processing and simulating T_B are utilized in an O-B study (section 3.1) to determine long-term drifts of MWR uncertainties at the ACTRIS site in Jülich, Germany. The results are compared to differences in T_B observations before and after an absolute calibration. For that analysis a long-term record of NWP model data is extracted from CLU. In a second example it is demonstrated how O-B for MWR can be used for bias correction in a field experiment involving multiple sites (section 3.2).

3.1 Long-term drift detection at Jülich

Figure 2: Model data availability from CLU at the Jülich site.

For comparing MWR measurements to simulated T_B to analyze long-term drifts at Jülich, NWP model data was extracted from the ACTRIS data centre unit CLU in the period June 2017 - December 2023 (Fig. 2), where continuous observations were made. CLU is archiving all NWP model data in a S3 repository at the Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI). The files, provided in the netCDF4 format, are open access and readily available by an API on the ACTRIS Cloudnet

¹Radiative transfer code: https://github.com/tobiasmarke/mwrpy_ret

data portal². The model files are harmonized and include consistent metadata, which ensures the quality and compatibility of each file. At Jülich the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasting (ECMWF) Integrated Forecast System (IFS) model data are available for the selected time period.

With the observation operator described in section 2.2 a long-term record of background T_B is simulated. Suitable clear-sky cases are selected by using a threshold of 0.5 K for the T_B standard deviation of the MWR window channel (31 GHz), which is most sensitive to liquid water clouds. A liquid water cloud free scene is required to persist for 60 minutes around the model output time and a median T_B is computed to compare to the observations. Figure 3 shows a one-year example period (2022) of the O-B analysis for all K-band channels, including two absolute calibration events. A drift starting around May, with increasing T_B of the observations, is visible before the first absolute calibration in July. After the calibration, differences of the same magnitude, but with higher background T_B , are suggesting a false calibration. This was corrected with a second calibration in September. Both calibrations result in a clear jump in O-B differences, which are comparable to those derived from measurements on the liquid nitrogen calibration target (cold load) before and after applying the updated calibration coefficients. This demonstrates that a drift and likely a false calibration were present and can be detected in the O-B comparison. A more in depth evaluation of the whole period, including more absolute calibration events, and analysis of additional MWR uncertainty aspects will be included and discussed in (Böck et al. 2024).

Figure 3: Example of K-band O-B differences (as seven day rolling median) for Jülich in 2022. Absolute calibration events are marked with a vertical dashed line.

²Cloudnet data portal: <https://cloudnet.fmi.fi>

3.2 O-B monitoring for bias correction (PANAME 2022)

O-B analysis can also be utilized to obtain bias-free T_B observations, which is necessary to improve MWR retrieval results and assimilation into NWP models, as shown in Martinet et al. (2020). For the study presented here, Météo-France has developed an O-B monitoring based on the fast radiative transfer model RTTOV-gb (De Angelis et al. 2016) as observation operator. T_B equivalent to the HATPRO MWR observations are simulated at all channels and all angles from 1-h forecasts of the French convective scale model AROME (Application of Research to Operations at MESoscale). A clear-sky selection to remove observations in cloudy conditions, based on thresholds on the 31 GHz 1 hour standard deviation was performed (similar to 3.1). This configuration for O-B monitoring has already been successfully applied for a MWR network (De Angelis et al. 2017) and has been adapted for the 2022 PANAME (PARis region urbaN Atmospheric observations and models for Multidisciplinary rEsearch) initiative, aiming for a better understanding of atmospheric and chemical processes. During the experiment, three HATPRO systems were deployed in and around the Paris urban region.

Investigation of the O-B diurnal cycle shows a dependency to atmospheric stability, with higher differences during stable cases, especially for opaque channels. Therefore, an additional criterion, of excluding cases with a temperature gradient between 500 m and 50 m of more than -2 K, was applied. As a result, differences in the opaque channels are reduced to the expected instrumental uncertainty and brightness temperatures measurements from all sites are thus comparable. The corresponding O-B inter-comparison of all instruments can be seen in Fig. 4. The large bias for the HATPRO deployed at Charles de Gaulle airport (MF CDG) shows that a correction needs to be applied for this unit for further comparisons. Further results showed improved humidity and temperature retrievals, compared to radiosonde data, when a TB bias correction is applied from this monitoring procedure.

4 Conclusions and outlook

In this VMG a framework to perform MWR observation minus background (O-B) comparisons, suitable for network configurations, is outlined. A software package for centralized MWR data processing and quality control is introduced to the ACTRIS Cloudnet chain and an implementation of a radiative transfer model was realized for T_B background calculations (see Chapter 2). The results shown in Chapter 3 demonstrate the importance of constantly monitoring drifts of MWR uncertainties by comparing observations with a model background for bias correction and an improved quality assessment, helping with instrument operation and maintenance.

With an increase in data availability in the ACTRIS network the selected methods and processing tools for O-B monitoring can be applied and criteria for stating

Figure 4: Inter-comparison of MWR biases for different elevation angles for the 2022 PANME experiment with additional thresholds : $T_{500m}-T_{50m} < -2$ K.

the data quality will be defined and tested for robustness, as some ACTRIS facilities just started to deliver MWR data to the central data hub. Collecting a sufficient amount of MWR data together with extracting the respective model profiles is necessary to provide consistent quality control across all sites. As a tool for statistical O-B analysis, the ReObs project (Chiriaco et al. 2018), which aims to synthesize, analyze and homogenize all ACTRIS observations in a single file, could be used. The developed framework of simulating T_B through an RT model will also be used to retrieve atmospheric parameters from MWR measurements within the ACTRIS MWR retrieval development efforts.

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